

The potential threat of the invasive Argentine ant to the survival of Fynbos native ant species

Natasha Mothapo and Theresa Wossler

DST/NRF Centre of Excellence for Invasion Biology, Department of Botany and Zoology, Private Bag XI, Matieland, 7602

Introduction

Much of our current knowledge of the impacts of the invasive Argentine ant on native Fynbos ants is based on bait and pitfall trap surveys. Argentine ants are known for their strong competitive abilities at both resource exploitation and interference competition, attributed to their high numeric abundance, unicolonial social organisation and aggression^{1,2}. These attributes contribute to their successful foraging strategies, often locating and retrieving food faster than native ants^{3,4}. We investigated the response of Fynbos native ant species to the invasive Argentine ant by evaluating their abilities in resource exploitation and interference competition, a function of their competitive ability and potential foraging success.

Materials and methods

Ant colonies were collected from Jonkershoek Nature Reserve and brought back to the laboratory where experimental colonies consisting of 500 workers, one queen and brood pieces were established.

Discovery time, Recruitment intensity and Resource assimilation, a measure of resource exploitation⁵ was tested with colonies of Argentine ants and native ants without a competitor. Resource competition was investigated by pairing a native ant colony with that of an Argentine ant colony and recording Discovery time, Recruitment intensity as well as levels of mortality as a result of interspecific aggression, a proxy for competition between the two species.

Acknowledgements

Stellenbosch HOPE project for funding. Shula Johnson and Andrew Fransman for assistance with fieldwork.

References

1. Holway, 1999 Ecology 80:232-251, 2. Holway et al. 2002, Ann. Rev. Ecology. Sys 33:181-233, 3. Human & Gordon, 1996, Oecologia 105:405-412, 4. Human & Gordon, 1999 Insect. Soc. 46:154-163, 5. Davidson, 1998 Ecol. Entomol 23:484-490

Results

Baseline: Resource exploitation

- None of the ants species investigated differed in their ability to discover the bait in the absence of a competitor ($F_{(4, 30)} = 0.82, p > 0.05$), although Argentine ants and the native *T. quadrispinosum* were faster than the other native ant species (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Error plot (Mean±SE) showing discovery time (s) of each species. There was no significant difference in the discovery time for each species in the absence of a competitor (One-Way ANOVA, $P > 0.05$).

- Argentine ants recruit to food faster and with greater intensity than native Fynbos ant (Fig. 2). However, none of the ants differed in the amount of bait retrieved during the 90 minute trial period ($F_{(4, 30)} = 2.16, p > 0.05$).

Figure 2. Recruitment curves (Mean±SE) for the five ant species representing the average pattern of recruitment to a fixed resource (bait) in the absence of a competitor.

Results

Interspecific resource competition

- Argentine ants did not locate the bait quicker than the native species, however, once they located it, they rapidly displaced native ants, monopolising the bait within the first 10mins of the trial (Fig.3).

Figure 3. Error plots (Mean±SE) showing the discovery times and recruitment patterns of each native species during interactions with the Argentine, as well as mortality rates for both Argentine ants and native ant species. The Argentine ants affected the recruitment patterns of all native species, with *L. capensis* being most severely affected (Pearson Correlation $***p < 0.001$), and was responsible for the high mortality of *A. custodiens* and *L. capensis* (Mann-Whitney U $***p < 0.001$).

P. capensis and *A. custodiens* suffered significant mortality through Argentine ant aggression. Their inability to compete with Argentine ants paints a bleak picture for the future of this biodiversity hotspot. This study shows no support for biotic resistance to Argentine ant invasion in the Fynbos.

